

Socio-Economic Evaluation of Women Workers in the Garment Industry in India: A Case Bangalore City

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Introduction

The More than half of the Population of the country Consist of women and therefore half of the potential work force is of the gender-based, any social, economic, or Industrial system that ignores the potential talents and special aptitudes of this half will be defective on many counts, it is, therefore, necessary to ensure equal opportunities and protection to the women of the country particularly to the women worker who are living in rural area from indignities.

India has 397 million labors out of which 125 million are women who constitute 31.23percent. A maximum of 106 million woman employees belong to rural areas and who also comprised of 26.70 percent and the remaining 18 million work in the urban areas. Only 10 percent of the labor work force is in the organized sector, which includes workers on regular salaries in registered companies and firms. The rest of the 93 percent labor force is in unorganized of the informal sector. The female work participation rate (W R) has increased from 19.7 percent in 1981 to 25.8 percent in 2011. As for manufacturing industries are concerned, about 1.1 percent of the total workforce are women employees in 2005, out of the total 19 percent of the total organized sector constituted by women workers.

The garment textile contributes 17.63% to the International trade earnings of India and it employs over 4.5 million labors. There are five different garment production hubs in India. All specialize in different types of garment production. Bangalore is one of the centers of production of the garment and has somewhere around 1300 big, small and medium-sized garment factories. A review of garment industries revealed that it is one of the largest manufacturing sectors in India. It accounts for nearly 20% of India's Industrial Output and 37% of India's Exports. Karnataka is known for being the apparel destination in the Global Market.

The Performance of the Indian Textile Industry

India is the highest producing of cloth and cotton after China. And third largest producer cotton in India among the world. The textile industry continues to be the second largest employment generating sector in India. It offers direct employment to over 35 million in the country. The share of textiles in total exports was 11.04% during April–July 2014–2015, as per the Ministry of Textiles. There were 2,500 textile weaving factories and 4,135 textile finishing factories in all over India. In the production of fabrics, the decentralized sector accounts for roughly 94 percent while the mill sector has a share of only 6 percent. Being an agro-based industry, the production of raw material varies from year to year depending on weather and rainfall conditions.

Garments Industry in Perspective and its Present Scenario- In Bangalore

The present study the Bangalore City has been selected as there is a concentration of industries located and women workers both skilled and unskilled being employed. Namely, Dasarahalli, Peenya Nelamangala, KR Puram Magadi, Road and Laggere In these area women are predominantly employed in textiles, plantations, garments, weaving, and other related industries. Today overseas buyers view Bangalore as an important location for sourcing of garments after Mumbai and Delhi. In Bangalore, Development of garments units was started in the 1970s onwards to lead the promoting of exports like Gokaldas and Ashoka export, Gokaldas Images, continental exports, Leela Fashions, Exports Overseas, etc. Later, small industries (fabricators) were started by taking the orders from the large scale.

The economy of Bangalore is contributed up with that of the readymade garment. More 30 percent of the Garments of the country are made in this region. The industry started flourishing and Most of Garment Industries are concentrated in Peenya industrial estate., goraguntepalya, and lagger. Nelamangala.

More than 3512 Garments units around in Bangalore as per recent survey report of 2014-16. Most of the buying agencies in the world have established their branch office in the city. Apart from this, Apparel Park, at Doddaballapur has started functioning in a big way. In Bangalore, garment units are mainly concentrated in the following area:. Bommanahalli, Bommasandra, Peenya, Yeswanthpur, Rajajinagar Industrial Estate and Industrial town.

Table 1 Present status of women workers in Ready Garment Factory 2009-2016

Year	Females	Females as % of total
2009-2010	1165043	87
2010-2011	1257807	88
2011-2012	1350001	89
2012-2013	1365000	90
2013-2014	1448102	91
2014-2015	1450004	93
2015-2016	1460008	93

Source: CMIE Report 2014-16

In the above table-1 Represent to the present status of women workers in garment factory in Karnataka in the above table shows the at beginning of the 2009-2010 around 1165043 females workers existing it 87% in the same 2015 to 2016 sum of 14,60008 females are represent in the percentage 93% but table shows rapidly increases in the female workers are migrate to the city.

Review of Literature

A review of the literature was added to this study by referring to a different journal and studies conducted by different individuals to show relevance to socio-economic status of women workers in Garments Factory.

Hate (2000) in her book stated that there is a positive change in the political, economic and social status of middle-class working and non-working women living in four cities in Maharashtra with the advent of independence.

Styles. Kapur (2004) has shown that the twin roles of women cause tension and conflict due to her social structure which is still more dominant. In her study on working women in Delhi, she has shown that traditional authoritarian set up of Hindu social structure continues to be the same basically and hence. Women face the problem of role conflict change in attitudes of men and women according to the situation can help to overcome their problem.

Rosen and Jerdee (2007) in their study stated that women were seen less favorably in terms of the knowledge, aptitudes, skills, motivation, interests, temperament, and work habits that are demanded in most managerial roles.

Sandhu and Singh (2008) reported that motivation factors viz. feeling of achievement, ability utilization, recognition and rewards, creative work freedom of expression and scope for professional growth contributed comparatively more to job satisfaction than factors like behavior of immediate officers, job security and advancement, adequacy of salary, administrative setup and social status attached to the job.

Drucker (2012) in his book stated that the labor force participation of married women under age fifty is now just as high as that of men. It is therefore unlikely to rise any further. But a very large number of women in the labor force the of those who entered when the inrush of women began are now reaching their mid-thirties. And also he states that most of the married women stay in the labor force after the first child.

Julia (2013) in her study that 'by focusing on women's careers the short-term objectives has been to correct the gender imbalance, but the long-term objective must be to develop theoretical concepts and explanation which the gender neutral and inclusive of both men and women. Second, the changes currently under way in work organization and professions will as well be referred to as providing new difficulties for women's careers as wells as presenting an opportunity for the re-conceptualization of the 'successful' career.

Amartys Sen. (2014) calls it, a sector of 'co-operative conflict', where there is different interest, expectation, contributions, needs and degrees of control.

Reddy and Venkateswarlu (2015) in their study concluded that farm scientists valued creativity and independence most in carrying out their tasks. They did not prefer to work in rural areas. The other work values of scientists differed slightly according to their age and experience.

The Review of this study reveals that the implications of Garment women Workers in Bangalore City. The Analysis of women's perceptions as factory workers shows that they are exploited on the factory floor in different ways and experience new forms of patriarchal domination beyond their family.

Origin Research Problem of the Women Workers in Garments Factory

Two-thirds of the garment workers are women and they have to struggle to make ends meet while putting up with the harsh daily reality of forced overtime, job insecurity and harassment at the factory work floor. Although all major brand companies have set up codes of conduct and audit mechanisms to ensure compliance with basic labor standards. The ground floor reality has not changed for the better and even seems to deteriorate as work pressure is rising due to

growing demand. Therefore, to improve the socio, Economic status and working conditions of women workers in the garment industry, they need to be empowered. So in This research paper to Examines Socio-economic status of women workers in Garments Industry with special reference to Bangalore city.

Objectives of the Study

The proposed research work consists of the following objectives.

- To study the working pattern and wages earnings of women workers in the Garment industry.
- To study job satisfaction and problems faced by women at the Work place.
- To study socio-economic condition of women workers in common life.
- To study the economic benefits derived by working women in their work place of industries.

Research Methodology

The present study is based on the Simple Random sampling method. The study is based on primary and secondary sources. The sample consists of women respondents from the different industrial area of Bangalore city. Total of 2500 samples has been selected for the study. To get more meaningful and useful respondents the tested questionnaire was used as a schedule and entries were made by the interview respondents answered the questions.

The secondary data compilation also took into consideration from Government reports, labor magazines, labor chronicle, labor review, Government Bulletins, State Government Reports.

Research Design

The present study the Bangalore City has been selected as there is a concentration of industries located and women workers both skilled and unskilled being employed. Namely, Dasarahalli, Penya Nelamangala, KR Puram Magadi, Road and Laggere In these area women are predominantly employed in textiles, plantations, garments, weaving, and other related industries. These workers are paid very negligible wages and no social security. It is very interesting to study the social, economic and educational status of women workers in these industries, and their problems. Hence in this particular field, 150 textiles industries and plantation related industries were selected for an interview and to inquiry about their existing problems. The development of the social and economic status of the working women and their employment in the industries and its impact on the family life of the working women has been considered for investigation. The size of the sample for the primary survey is. 2500 working women.

Statistical Tools

The data and information have been analyzed with the help of statistical tools such as averages, percentages, simple and compound growth rates and multiple regression analysis for both secondary and primary data of the study.

Limitation of the Study

The present study is restricted for the need, scope and objectives. It also has certain conditions. Since there is no systematic, maintenance of records, data collection was difficult and data was not available for the recent years of women workers of different selected industries.

The study is based on the questionnaire and the responses for women workers could be causal. The accuracy of the information provided by the respondents in the personal data could not be established. As based on the survey to the following findings and measures are discussed.

Major Findings of the Study

- Realizing the need for quality data on garment workers, it was decided to conduct a sample survey of garment workers in Bengaluru city. A large sample of 2500 workers was drawn from the list of registered garment manufacturing units and the total number of workers employed in these units which were made available at the Office of the Commissioner of Labour, Govt. of Karnataka. As per the list, there are 854 registered garment manufacturing units. A total number of workers employed in these units is 1,95,943 of which 64,045 are men and 1,31,898 are women. One percent of the total number of workers which comes to 2500 is the sample size of the survey. Simple Random Method was employed to select the workers for the purpose of collecting information using holding interviews. Certain conclusions have emerged out of this survey.
- The overwhelming majority of workers in the garment industry is women. 72.8 percent of the sample is women and 27.2 percent are men. Similarly, a large majority of workers are rural migrants. Out of the 2500 sample, 1859 have come from within Karnataka. 31.1 percent have come from Bangalore rural district. 35.4 percent have come from the neighboring districts of Chikkaballapur, Kolar, Ramanagaram and Tumkur. 24.63 percent comes from Hassan, Mandya and Mysore. Garment workers come from almost all castes though 21.6 percent are SC's; 5.6 percent are ST's; 6.8 percent belong to Category - I. Large percentage of 35.7 come from Category - IIIA. However, Brahmins are excluded. The average size of the family of garment workers ranges from a minimum of 3 to a maximum of 5.
- Three members could be the average size of the family. Little less than 50 percent of the sample, i.e., 43 percent have studied up to S.S.L.C. Only 2.2 percent are graduates. 71.1 percent live in rented houses. As far as possible they take a house near to the place of work. 91.6 percent reported having toilet facilities at home.
- Nearly 50 percent do not have safe drinking water tap connections at home while little more than 50 percent reported having that at home. 50 percent of the workers reported having land though of low-size land-holdings which means the majority of the workers having land are marginal and small farmers. Nearly 50 percent reported not having land. The average size of the land holding would be around 2 acres.
- Employment conditions are another issue looked into in some detail. Unlike the workers in the organized sector, garment workers seem not to bother much about their status. They look at work in a garment factory as the sole source of livelihood. As many as 67.6 percents are temporary workers, followed by 2.5 percent of contract workers, less than 1 percent casual workers and 29.1 percent are those who have some stability of job if not job security.
- As many as 56.9 percents of the sample are highly skilled workers, followed by 23 percent are the unskilled workers, 12.05 percent are the skilled workers and 8 percent are semi-skilled workers. Little more than half of the sample represents highly skilled workers, i.e., those who engage themselves in tailoring, cutting and designing given the informal nature of employment in the garment industry.
- Little more than half of the sample secures jobs through informal social network like friends, relatives and well-wishers followed by 41.7 percent reported having got jobs through direct interviews. Of the sample reported having worked continuously for up to 5 years. About the mode of transport the overwhelming majority of workers, i.e., 91 percent of the workers depend on any and every means of transport like BMTC, an auto rickshaw. As many as 41.3 percents go to work by walk and a least of 9 percent reported to go by company vehicles.
- A large majority, i.e., 80 percent of the sample have come from villages while little more than 20 percent are locals. 85 percent of the workers reported to work 8 hours per day, 98

percent reported to get a lunch break and 69.5 percent reported to have got canteen facilities. Regarding paid sick leave, little less than 50 percent reported that they get paid leave while another 51 percent said negatively. 75 percent of the workers reported getting compensation in case of accidents at work place.

- 99.9 percent reported they had got a toilet facility and the perception of the quality of the toilet facility is good. 73 percent of the workers reported they experience difficulties while performing their job. Increasing work pressure has been reported by 78.3 percent times. Strangely abuse by supervisors seems to have reduced as it was mentioned only 17.5 percent times. Workers seem to be happy with the wages they are getting.
- Compliance of government measures is extremely poor except that 90 percent of the workers reported being getting a daily wage of up to Rs.250, far more than the daily wage fixed by Government of Karnataka. Majority of the workers, i.e., 62.8 percent are not aware of the minimum wages fixed by the government. 53.1 percent are getting their wages through cash and 47 percent are getting through cheque and ATM's. 81.6 percent of workers have subscribed to provident fund scheme though they do not know exactly how to get the benefit under the scheme.
- The trade union movement in the garment industry in Bangalore city is weak and a large number of workers i.e., 73 percent reported that unions do not exist. Management not permitting the workers, lack of proper information and fear of victimization has been mentioned as significant reasons for not having unions. The question of the settlement of demands hardly matters as the management seems to decide everything and implement the decisions through an executive order. Workers are not able to protect themselves because of the lack of unions and low awareness of the unions.

Suggestions

- The conclusions are mixed. Barring payment of wages, workers in the garment industry hardly get any fringe benefits. A plethora of legislations and government schemes exist to ensure that workers are provided with minimum benefits of welfare and well-being like paid-leave, maternity benefit, medical and educational facilities. There is a need, therefore, to sensitize all the stake holders: employers, government officials and trade unions towards the plight of the unorganized workers in general and garment industry in particular. Gender sensitization needs to be created. For this educational, research institutions, NGO's and trade unions must carry on a sustained campaign through seminars, workshops and street plays.
- There is a need to strengthen the government departments concerned with labor. Efficiency, if any, in man-power has to be made good by filling up the vacancies.
- There is a need for a change of heart on the part of the mainstream trade unions. Sooner they come out of the ideological baggage in which they have been trapped the better for the workers and trade unions.
- The government departments must work out sound procedures and mechanisms to identify the beneficiaries among the workers to ensure that the benefits under the government schemes do reach the needy. There is, therefore, a need to create a database of unorganized labor. The present survey is a modest attempt in that direction.

Conclusion

Recognition of women workers and providing proper jobs to suit their qualifications and experiences providing equal rights and wages under labor economy is in practice in advanced countries, which is the issue to be implemented in the new millennium in developing country like

India. It is an emerging issue which will be given due consideration by both the State and Central Governments for the upliftment of women work force in particular society, in general, and for the total development of National Economy as a whole.

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